

INTERFERENCE IN THE COMMUNICATION PROCESS AND THE FACTORS CAUSING IT AS WELL AS ITS NEGATIVE EFFECT ON LANGUAGE LEARNING

Istoda Rasulova

teacher of the Samarkand State
Institute of Architecture and Construction,
e-mail: istoda.87@gmail.com
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7992892>

Abstract

The article describes linguistic and cultural interference, interference errors, their causes, views on interference, types of interference, ways to eliminate speech errors related to interference, which occur in the process of learning a foreign language.

Keywords: Interlingual interference, linguistic and cultural interference, bilingualism, internal interference, external interference, phonetic, grammatical interference.

When it comes to contrastive linguistics, first of all, it is necessary to determine its place among other areas of linguistics. Contrastive linguistics - when it was formed as a separate direction of linguistics, this field took its place among such directions as comparative-historical linguistics, areal linguistics, cross-linguistics, typological linguistics, linguistics of universals, contact linguistics. and it would be appropriate if we could define its specific aspects. Because each of the listed areas work on the basis of comparing languages, they differ from each other according to their goals. Blending is the main (perhaps the only) method of language learning. However, the directions of linguistics working on the basis of the hybrid method differ according to the object and purpose of study: comparative-historical linguistics - to describe the general evolution of related languages and their evolution in time and space; areal linguistics - regardless of whether languages belong to the same language family, it consists in determining their common aspects, territorial division, describing isoglosses (a line drawn on geographical maps to show the distribution area of a language); university linguistics is one of the theoretical directions of linguistics, which studies the common features of languages, regardless of whether they belong to a common family, and consists in determining the nature of human language and its mechanism; Contact Linguistics is the analysis of interlinguistic relations and changes occurring in these countries as a result of political, economic, and cultural changes in different parts of the world; cross-linguistics - identification of the similar and different aspects of languages, regardless of the proximity of their origin, contrastive linguistics - peculiarities in the language system are subjected to contrast analysis on the basis of contradiction.

On the other hand, multilingualism is an integral part of the modern sociolinguistic situation, therefore, defining new tasks in the field of education, preparing students for a multicultural and multinational environment are among the problems that need to be taken into account in teaching foreign languages. In this direction, the necessary scientific recommendations have been examined and the necessary scientific recommendations have been developed: one of the tasks that must be introduced into language education is to eliminate the negative consequences of the interaction of interacting languages in a language environment with multilingual communicative relations. is to develop effective technologies.

Everyone wants to know a foreign language in addition to their mother tongue and to speak it perfectly. Language experience is initially formed in the student, during the learning of the mother tongue. Three languages - mother tongue, Russian and a foreign language - are taught in primary classes of general secondary schools. The students' language experience is a set of knowledge, skills and abilities collected from these three languages, and its size, scope of application and issues of interdependence are within the framework of the principle of taking into account the language experience of the methodology. It is observed that the students' language experience hinders (negative effect - interference) or helps (positive effect - transposition) in learning a foreign language.

Interlanguage relations occur when representatives of two different languages or dialects speak or write to each other. In other words, speech communication between two or more speakers is a language relationship. For example, Uzbek-Tajik language contact occurs when Uzbeks and Tajiks speak to each other, that is, when they enter into language contact. In this case, when an Uzbek and a Tajik speak Uzbek, the reference language is Uzbek. If they speak Tajik, the reference language will be Tajik. But they can also speak Russian. In this case, the Russian language is the third language used as a means of communication, which is called the "mediating language". As a result of language relationship, languages can move away from each other or move closer to each other. Moving away is called "divergence", approaching "convergence". In order for a language relationship to take place, one or both of the parties must know the mother tongue and the other party's language or the intermediary language. Knowledge of two languages is called "bilingualism" (bilingualism), and a person who knows two languages is called "bilingv". A bilingual can incorrectly transfer the rules of one language to another. This phenomenon is called "interference". Interference mainly occurs when the rules of the mother tongue are transferred to another language.

It is known that teaching a foreign language provides comprehensive coverage of the studied phenomenon. Based on existing research, it seems possible to identify and classify the main causes of interference incidents within the framework of the following four-component system:

- linguistic;
- psychological;
- sociolinguistic;
- methodologically inappropriate.

Linguistic factors that determine the emergence and development of interference include, first of all, inconsistencies and similarities of the languages of communication.

U. Weinreich says that "interference is always related to the language structure, as if it is a specific response of the language structure to a foreign element that has entered it" [Weinreich, 1979:12]. It should be noted that determining the cause of interference only by similarities or, on the contrary, by differences in the structure of languages seems to be oversimplified. It can be assumed that the closeness of these specific structures creates the most favorable conditions for the emergence of a mixture of interacting languages, the founder of the Saratov Linguistic School, L.I. facilitates the development of bilingualism and, consequently, the emergence of interference ... but the very closeness of the languages itself limits its development. The existence of a large number of similar links in systems determines certain limits of interrelated languages, because the latter emerges precisely on the basis of similarity and difference" [Barannikova, 1996:16]. Thus, it is fair to call the linguistic causes of

interference phenomena similarities and differences in the system of interacting languages.

Undoubtedly, the degree of formation of speech skills in the studied foreign language is a joint factor: the lack of perfect knowledge of the language creates favorable conditions for the occurrence of interference, and on the contrary, the development of skills helps to reduce the level of interference. When considering the linguistic causes of interference, we believe that the conditions of the communicative act, more precisely, the complex criteria such as the characteristics of the communication field and its participants, are not less important. When it comes to everyday communication, the participants of communication can ignore the accuracy of pronunciation and compliance with some grammatical norms, in an academic environment, the content and form of formal speech is ensured to be clear and clear, and as a result, possible interferences are ensured. control is created. It is also appropriate to take into account the bilingual or monolingual nature of the interlocutor in communicative communication. Bilingualism of the interlocutor and the awareness of the speaker's ability to understand in the transition from language to language or in mixed forms will help to manifest interference disorders in his speech, and the monolingual speech of the interlocutor will allow more careful control of the correctness of speech and serves as an incentive to suppress potential interference. [Weinreich, 1972:22]

As W. Weinreich pointed out, not only linguistic, but also extralinguistic factors should be taken into account in the study of interference [Weinreich, 1972:56]. Continuing to classify the reasons for the emergence and development of interference, we distinguish a psychological group, among which we consider such a factor as language ability.

A. A. Leontyev, a well-known expert in the field of psychology and linguistics, defines linguistic ability as follows: "Language ability is a set of psychological and physiological conditions that ensure the assimilation, production, reproduction and adequate perception of language signs by members of the linguistic community " [Lyontiev. 2010:54]. Based on this definition, it can be assumed that the weak development of linguistic abilities is one of the main psychological reasons for a certain disorder in speech, because in this case, the level of acceptance and mastery of the signs of one language to transfer them to another decreases.

Another important aspect is the relationship between the emotional state of the speaker (as well as his level of fatigue) and the level of interference. As evidence of our opinion, it is appropriate to refer to the words of U. Weinreich: "Overcoming interference requires actions that are not always easy" [Weinreich, 1979:54]. In this case, it is appropriate to talk about the psychological efforts and emotional stress necessary to control the prevention of confusion between the norms of the native and the studied languages, which cause many interference errors for the speaker.

The following factor influencing the emergence of interference has a syncretic nature, namely, in the mind of the speaker, it is related to both psychology and sociolinguistic bilingualism. Well-known American psychologist Ch. Osgood and sociolinguist S. M. Erwin in the 50s of the 20th century divided bilingualism into two types: "compound" (compound) and "coordinate" (coordinate). To study this situation of bilingualism, language acquisition is classified as follows: in the case of learning languages in a "mixed" environment (frequent switching from one language to another at school and at home is practiced to express the same meanings), " "complex" type is formed, and "coordinate" bilingualism refers to the transition from one language to another when the environment or activity changes [Weinreich. 241-253].

In the first case, languages form interconnected parts of a unified system in the mind of the speaker, and in coordinate bilingualism, separate existing systems with significant functional independence of languages. Based on this, we believe that complex bilingualism is more conducive to the manifestation and development of interference, and the coordinate type of bilingualism leads to fewer interference errors.

Sociolinguistic factors that cause interference in the speaker's speech should include, first of all, socio-historical conditions related to language. We agree with the opinion of L. I. Barannikova, who writes as follows: "Among the factors affecting the level of development of interference, first of all, the existence of general socio-historical conditions, the speakers of the languages with which they communicate are considered. The size of contact groups is of great importance, the level of development of their languages (the presence of old written traditions, etc.) [Barannikova.1966.12]. In addition to the factors listed by the linguist, in our opinion, the social status of the language, the granting of the state status to the language, which directly affects its authority, and as a result, can be expressed by the attitude to the purity of the language and its compliance with its standards. Based on this, the next social relationship that we have mentioned is derived. According to W. Weinreich, "in some societies, switching from one language to another is considered normal, and in others, it is given negative merit. If interference is allowed in one language, it is condemned in the second language. As an example, the author cites English in Canada French presents a situation of bilingualism: the attitude to the interference situation can be both personal and social in nature. on the contrary, when speaking English with an accent, it can be useful in terms of its origin and position [Weinrich. 1979:53].

Having determined the causes of interference phenomena, such as linguistic, psychological, sociolinguistic features (as well as the junctions of these fields), we begin to consider methodological factors, we will first of all address them to the approach and the teaching method determined by it. A group of methods based on a conscious approach, among which the most common in the methodology is intellectually practical and comparative learning, leaves little chance for interference to occur. In order to reduce the influence of one language on another, it is appropriate to compare the similarities and differences between the system of the studied language and the system of one's mother tongue. Perfect knowledge of the mother tongue is an important factor in learning a second language.

Thus, the interference is mainly formed by the participation of four aspects - the language norm, the behavior of bilinguals, interlinguistic relations with the mother tongue, and social conditions. Based on these aspects, they created the following four-dimensional typology of interference:

- 1) due to deviation from the language norm (linguistic aspect);
- 2) according to the peculiarities of speech activity of the bilingual (bilingual) (psychological aspect);
- 3) according to the relationship between the mother tongue and the languages being studied (interlinguistic aspect);
- 4) according to the social situation (socio-ethnological aspect) [Karlinsky. 1989:60].

Interference is a phenomenon that is beyond the control of the speaker. Its amount corresponds to the growth of a person's acquisition of a second language and disappears when the language is fully mastered. The structural cause of interference depends on the differences at each level of the two languages, and the non-structural causes are equal to the

psychological laws of interlinguistic equalization. Of all the phenomena resulting from the interaction of languages (interference, transference, intercalation, transcalation), only interference can be predicted, that is, the linguist can predict the phenomenon of interference as a result of identifying similarities and differences by comparing two languages. Other phenomena cannot be known in advance, because their formation depends on the influence of many extralinguistic aspects.

For example, in Uzbek, the word "fox" is pronounced softly, even if the letter "f" is not followed by a sign that means softness. But when Russians want to write the word "fox", they write and pronounce it in the style of "fox". These disadvantages cause difficulties in language learning.

It is important to study not only theoretical issues of phonetic interference errors (causes, types), but also didactic and psychological aspects of their prevention and elimination of errors. For example, Methodist Q. Kadirova explained the causes of phonetic interference in teaching Arabic to Uzbek students [Kadirova. 2008:11]

He cites the following opinion of O.A. Yamshchikova: "Phonetic interference is the result of effective influence on the skills formed by keying as the leader of a certain system of skills. One of the main features of phonetic interference as a psychological phenomenon in the methodology of teaching another language leads to the violation of listening and pronunciation skills as a result of interaction and the opposite reception of the phonetic system of the language being studied.

Methodist scientist V.S. Dmitriyeva cites the following opinion of the well-known linguist N.S. Trubetskoi, who paid special attention to the problem of bilingualism in the field of linguistics: "Usually, in the process of listening and analyzing speech, we unwittingly use our "phonological filters" that are considered primary in the native language. The fact that our "filters" do not correspond to another language (this is natural, of course) creates a number of errors and misunderstandings. The sounds of a foreign language are also susceptible to incorrect phonological interference in our language. [Dmitriyeva. 2011:53]. So, the accent in a foreign language is not the inability to pronounce one or another sound, but it is related to the "misjudgment of the sound" based on the differences in the phonological system of the native language and the foreign language.

At the initial stage of language learning, the sounds of a foreign language are studied side by side with the sounds of the native language. A relatively common type of phonetic interference is interference based on similarity, which is usually a direct result of the pronunciation skills of the mother tongue in the acquisition of speech sounds of the studied foreign language to similar sounds. will be associated with decay.

Methodists divide skills into three groups: 1) transferring native language skills to new language information; 2) transferring the skills previously formed in the mother tongue to new language information; 3) newly formed skills. From this, according to S.G. Nikolayev [Nikolayev.1990:132], it can be concluded that there are three different approaches to teaching a foreign language, taking into account the characteristics of the mother tongue: 1) comparing facts and similarities in two languages, and by similarity mastering; 2) comparing facts in two languages and establishing proximity, mastering similarities and differences; 3) to compare the facts of two languages and establish those that do not match, mastering on the basis of contrast. If we consider the Uzbek language as a mother tongue and the Turkish language from the perspective of a foreign language, then all three of the above approaches

can be used in practice. Both languages belong to the same language family, so they have something in common. But the Uzbek and Russian languages belong to different language families, so differences in these languages are more important.

It is important to take into account the experience of teaching speech in the mother tongue when teaching children a second language. For example, mastering the articulation of individual sounds is the most difficult task for a child. O.I. Solovyeva, marking the main directions of work on the education of the sound culture of speech, "in front of the teacher, teach children to pronounce the sounds in words cleanly, to pronounce words correctly in accordance with the rules of orthography of the language, to pronounce clearly emphasizes that they have the task of training expressive speech. [Solovyova. 1996:50-51]

Therefore, when learning a language, first of all, it is necessary to pay attention to correct hearing and correct pronunciation. The language learning process becomes easier and easier only if we pronounce the sounds cleanly and cleanly.

References:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh. ta'lim sifat va samaradorligini oshirishda innovatsion yondashuv. – Guliston: 2018
2. Вайнрайх У. Одноязычие и многоязычие. В "Новое в лингвистике" / Под ред. В.Ю. Розенцвейга. / Вып. 6. М.: Изд. Прогресс, 1972. Б. 25-60.
3. Любимова Н.А. Фонетическая интерференция. -Л.: Изд-во ЛГУ, 1985. -55-бет.
4. Карлинский А.Е. Экспериментальное изучение лексической интерференции в прикладных целях // -Алма-Ата, 1989, Б.60.
5. Вишневская, Г.М. Билингвизм и его аспекты [Текст] / Г.М. Вишневская. – Иваново, 1997. – Б. 100.
6. Дмитриева, Ю.В. Проблема межъязыковой интерференции в преподавании иностранных языков в вузе Электронный ресурс. / Ю.В. Дмитриева. Сайт Саратовского государственного университета имени Чернышевского. Режим доступа: <http://www.sgu.rti/files/nodes/13579/Dmitrieva.doc>. - Загл. с экрана
8. Соловьева О.И. Методика развития речи и обучения родному языку в детском саду. 3-нашр. М., 1996, 50-51-бетлар.
9. К. С. Кодирова. Преодоление фонетической интерференции при обучении арабскому языку узбекской аудитории: Дис. ...канд. пед. наук. Т., 2008.
10. Николаев, С.Г. К вопросу о грамматической интерференции и путях ее преодоления в рамках курса интенсивного обучения [Текст] / С.Г. Николаев // Интенсивное обучение иностранным языкам. – М.: Изд-во МГУ, 1990. – Б.132.
11. Islamova D., Jalilova M. Some comments on Uzbek folk proverbs. Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research Journal. Volume: 10, Issue: 5. – India, May 2021. – P.410-414. (Impact factor: SJIF 7.69.) DOI: 10.5958/2278-4853.2021.00424.9 <https://indianjournals.com/ijor.aspx?target=ijor:ajmr&volume=10&issue=5&article=061>